

ASSESSING THE ROLE OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT IN ACHIEVING MATH LEARNING GOALS: A GOAL-BASED EVALUATION

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Assessing the Role of Formative Assessment in Achieving Math Learning Goals: A Goal-Based Evaluation

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Abstract

Formative assessment as outlined in Department Order No. 8, s. 2015, is an ongoing process that helps teachers and students identify strengths and weaknesses to improve learning. Given the challenges students face in Mathematics as evidenced by low proficiency levels in a school at Central Mindanao, Philippines, teachers play a crucial role in enhancing learning, which can be evaluated systematically using Ralph Tyler's goal-based evaluation model. The study aims to determine the alignment of formative assessments with learning goals, their role in achieving these goals, and the subsequent actions for improvement. Employing a descriptive evaluation research design with a quantitative approach, the study utilized an adopted checklist validated by five mathematics experts, achieving an Aiken's Content Validity Index of 0.96. Data sources included GRACE PASS results, curriculum maps, formative assessments, and quarter examination results, analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Findings revealed that formative assessments were well-aligned with curriculum goals, effectively fostering student self-regulation, introspection, and targeted learning strategies, while enabling teachers to provide timely feedback as evidenced by the content of the instrument (for the learner) with a mean of 3.77 and an SD of .22 which is interpreted as very evident, the content of the instrument (for the teacher) with a mean of 3.85 and an SD of .22 which is interpreted as very evident, the alignment of the instrument to the curriculum with a mean of 3.88 and an SD of .21 which is interpreted as very evident, and Pre and Post Test result of the respondents. However, gaps were identified in the preparatory phase of lessons, suggesting the need for improved diagnostic tools and enhanced alignment of before the lesson activities with curriculum standards. These insights underscore the significant role of formative assessments in enhancing student performance and engagement in mathematics. By addressing identified gaps and providing targeted support, formative assessments can further contribute to meaningful learning experiences and academic success in mathematics education.

Keywords: goal-based evaluation model, evaluation, mathematics, k to 12 curriculum, formative assessment

Introduction

According to Department Order number 8, series of 2015 entitled Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program of the Department of Education Republic of the Philippines, formative assessment is an ongoing, informal process that helps both teachers and students by identifying strengths and weaknesses, guiding improvements in teaching and learning. Teachers use evidence from these assessments to adjust their instruction and support student progress, with results not impacting final grades but instead fostering a deeper understanding of students' needs. This approach encourages students to reflect on their learning, receive immediate feedback, and take responsibility for their own academic growth.

Mathematics is said to be one of the most difficult subjects. According to the pre-test result of the Global Resources for Assessment Curriculum and Evaluation Performance Assessment of Standards and Skills (GRACE PASS) from the Phoenix Publishing House Inc. and Sibers Publishing House Inc., 168 or 74.0% are developing, 42 or 18.5% are beginning, 17 or 7.5% are approaching proficiency, and 0 or 0.0% are proficient and advanced in Mathematics particularly in Grade 10 of one school in Central Mindanao. As this subject is said to be difficult, teachers play a great role in helping the students to level up their learning and achieve learning goals in math.

Evaluation is a systematic process used to measure and determine the value or effectiveness of programs, activities, or objectives, often comparing achieved outcomes to predetermined standards to guide decision-making (Muryadi, 2017; Nurman, 2016). Tyler's goal-based evaluation model, introduced in the mid-20th century, emphasizes assessing whether learning objectives or program goals have been achieved, typically through pretests and posttests, making it a widely used and time-efficient approach in education and other fields (Putra, 2018; Novalinda et al., 2020).

Research Questions

In this study, the formative assessments in Grade 10 Mathematics of a school in Central Mindanao will be evaluated through goal-based evaluation by Ralph Tyler. The following questions namely:

1. What are the goals of formative assessments in achieving math learning goals?
2. How well are formative assessments aligned with and supporting the achievement of math learning goals?
3. What actions will be taken based on the findings? will be addressed at the end of the study thereby determine if the learning goals are achieved?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive evaluation research with a quantitative approach. The evaluation approach used is the Goal-Based Evaluation Model of Ralph Tyler.

Respondents

The object being evaluated was the formative assessments of Grade 10 Mathematics in one school in Central Mindanao, Philippines.

Instrument

An adopted checklist based on Department Order number 8, series of 2015 entitled Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program of the Department of Education Republic of the Philippines validated by five mathematics experts was utilized to find out the content validity of the instrument. The five-point Likert scale used were 5 – Excellent, 4 – Very Good, 3 – Good, 2 – Fair, and 1 – Needs Improvement. Using the Aiken's Content Validity Index, the content validation resulted to a value of 0.96 which says that the instrument is very valid. Aiken's Validity Index as narrated in the study of Irawan and Wiluyeng (2020) as cited in the study of Baybayan (2024) was calculated through the formula, wherein V = Validity of Aiken's Index, S = The score awarded by the rater minus the lowest possible rating a rater can award, C = The highest possible rating a rater can award, and N = The number of raters rating the test questionnaire. The Validity of Aiken's Index or V obtained in each item is then classified by Irawan and Wilujeng (2020) into different categories with respective decisions, namely $0 \leq V \leq 0.4$ as Invalid, $0.4 < V \leq 0.8$ Medium Validity, and $0.8 < V \leq 1$ Very Valid.

Moreover, the instruments were the Global Resources for Assessment Curriculum and Evaluation Performance Assessment of Standards and Skills (GRACE PASS) results from the Phoenix Publishing House Inc. and Sibs Publishing House Inc., the curriculum map from the Department of Education, and the formative assessments and the quarter examination results from the Grade 10 Mathematics teacher. The formative assessments were evaluated by five Mathematics experts using the four-point Likert Scale namely, 4 – Very Evident, 3 – Somehow Evident, 2 – Rarely Evident, and 1 – Not Evident.

Procedure

A formal letter addressed to the president of one school in Central Mindanao, Philippines was sent for approval in gathering the resources needed for the study namely, lesson plans which includes the formative assessments, GRACE PASS result as basis for the pre-test score and quarter examination scores of the students as post-test. After the approval, the researcher asked the approval from the principal of the school to obtain the lesson plans and quarter examination scores from the Grade 10 Mathematics teacher and the GRACE PASS result from the Data Information Management and Analysis Officer of the school. After obtaining the documents, the researcher asked the evaluators to evaluate the formative assessments in the lesson plans. After that the evaluators evaluated the formative assessments, the evaluation was gathered, encoded, and analyzed by the researcher.

Data Analysis

After gathering the evaluation results from the experts, the researcher computed for the mean and standard deviation and interpreted the data. Moreover, the GRACE PASS result and the Quarter Examination Result were compared. Moreover, the content of the instrument (for the learner), the content of the instrument (for the teacher), and the alignment of the instrument to the curriculum were interpreted as follows, namely, 3.50 – 4.00 Very Evident, 2.50 – 3.49 Somehow Evident, 1.50 – 2.49 Rarely Evident, and 1.00 – 1.49 Not Evident. The pre and post test result as evidenced by the GRACE PASS Result and Quarter Exam Result were interpreted as follows, namely, 0 – 19% Beginning, 20 – 39% Developing, 40 – 59% Approaching Proficiency, 60 – 79% Proficient, and 80 – 100% Advanced.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that ethical standards were strictly followed in conducting the study. Key ethical principles such as the beneficence, justice, autonomy, and transparency were emphasized. Furthermore, the study aimed to benefit the educational institution by evaluating the formative assessments to enhance learning in mathematics. The research process upheld fairness, autonomy, and transparency. The researcher transparently communicated the study's results to stakeholders and ensured proper authorization for publication.

The study was conducted without any material compensation or sponsorship, relying entirely on the researcher's self-funding. Various ethical measures, such as confidentiality pledges, and privacy safeguards, were implemented to protect the school. The study also ensured that no personal information would be disclosed, maintaining strict confidentiality in handling data.

The research methodology included data collection procedures, and compliance with institutional approvals. The study focused on the formative assessments. The researcher followed a structured process, obtaining necessary permissions from school authorities before conducting the study. Additionally, proper documentation was followed.

Results and Discussion

This presents the findings of the study, its analysis, and interpretations. The first part presents the Aiken’s Content Validity Result of the adopted checklist based on Department Order number 8, series of 2015 entitled Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program of the Department of Education Republic of the Philippines validated by five mathematics experts. The second part presents the evaluation result of the Content of the Instrument (For the Learner) and the Content of the Instrument (For the Teacher) of the created formative assessments for Grade 10 Mathematics. The third part presents the Alignment of the Instrument to the Curriculum of the created Grade 10 Mathematics formative assessments to the school and Department of Education (DepEd) curriculum map. The fourth part presents the Pre and Post Test result of the respondents as presented through the Global Resources for Assessment Curriculum and Evaluation Performance Assessment of Standards and Skills (GRACE PASS) results from the Phoenix Publishing House Inc. and Sibs Publishing House Inc. and the quarterly examination scores.

Table 1. Aiken’s Content Validity Result

Item Number	Aiken’s Index Validator 1	Aiken’s Index Validator 2	Aiken’s Index Validator 3	Aiken’s Index Validator 4	Aiken’s Index Validator 5	SI	S2	S3	S4	S5	S	V	Decision	
I. Content Of The Instrument														
A. For Learner														
A1	3	5	4	5	5	2	4	3	4	4	17	0.85	Very Valid	
A2	3	5	5	5	5	2	4	4	4	4	18	0.90	Very Valid	
A3	3	5	4	5	5	2	4	3	4	4	17	0.85	Very Valid	
A4	3	5	4	5	5	2	4	3	4	4	17	0.85	Very Valid	
B1	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
B2	4	5	4	5	5	3	4	3	4	4	18	0.90	Very Valid	
B3	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
B4	4	4	5	5	5	3	3	4	4	4	18	0.90	Very Valid	
B5	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
C1	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
C2	5	5	4	5	5	4	4	3	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
B. For Teacher														
A1	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
A2	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
A3	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
A4	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
B1	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
B2	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
B3	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
B4	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
B5	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
B6	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
C1	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
C2	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
C3	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
II. Alignment Of The Instrument To The Curriculum														
A1	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
A2	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	4	19	0.95	Very Valid	
B1	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
B2	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
C1	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
C2	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	20	1.00	Very Valid	
												Overall	0.96	Very Valid

Table 1 presents the validity of the instrument through Aiken’s Content Validity Index. This further reveal that all of the items are very valid with an overall validity of 0.96. This further reveal that items A2, B2, B3, B4, B6, C1, C2, and C3 in the content of the instrument for the teacher and items B1, B2, C1, and C2 in the alignment of the instrument to the curriculum got a validity of 1.00. Moreover, items B1, B3, B5, C1, and C2 in the content of the instrument for the learners, items A1, A2, A4, B1, and B5 in the content of the instrument for the teacher, and items A1 and A2 in the alignment of the instrument to the curriculum got a validity of 0.95. Following this, items A2, B2, and B4 in the content of the instrument for the learners got a validity of 0.90. Finally, items A1, A3, and A4 in the content of the instrument for the learners got a validity of 0.85.

Table 2 presents the content of the instrument (for the learner). This further reveal that most of the items are seen in the formative assessments with an overall mean of 3.766 which is interpreted as very evident. This finding affirms that formative assessments capture key aspects of the learners’ engagement and reflection in the learning process.

Table 2. Content of the Instrument (For the Learner)

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
<i>The formative assessments lets' the learner...</i>			
A. Before The Lesson			
1. Know what s/he knows about the topic/lesson	3.71	.50	Very Evident
2. Understand the purpose of the lesson and how to do well in the lesson	3.66	.48	Very Evident
3. Identify ideas or concepts s/he misunderstands	3.63	.57	Very Evident
4. Identify barriers to learning	3.57	.61	Very Evident
B. During The Lesson			
1. Identify one's strengths and weaknesses	3.86	.18	Very Evident
2. Identify barriers to learning	3.77	.33	Very Evident
3. Identify factors that help him/her learn	3.86	.18	Very Evident
4. Know what s/he knows and does not know	3.80	.24	Very Evident
5. Monitor his/her own progress	3.77	.24	Very Evident
C. After The Lesson			
1. Tell and recognize whether s/he met learning objectives and success criteria	3.91	.13	Very Evident
2. Seek support through remediation, enrichment, or other strategies	3.89	.12	Very Evident
Overall	3.77	.32	Very Evident

Note: 3.50 – 4.00 Very Evident, 2.50 – 3.49 Somehow Evident, 1.50 – 2.49 Rarely Evident, 1.00 – 1.49 Not Evident

Moreover, item number 1 in after the lesson “Tell and recognize whether s/he met learning objectives and success criteria” got the highest rated mean of 3.91 which is interpreted as very evident. This reflects the strong emphasis placed on the ability of the students against the set goals. This is also a critical component of formative assessment for this encourages self-regulation and goal-oriented behavior among students. This is followed by item number 2 in after the lesson “Seek support through remediation, enrichment, or other strategies” with a mean of 3.89 which is interpreted as very evident. This emphasizes the importance of post-lesson interventions and suggests that learners value and recognize the necessity of seeking assistance in enhancing understanding and mastery making it a key element of the learning process. The third of which is item number 1 in during the lesson “Identify one's strengths and weaknesses” and item number 3 in during the lesson “Identify factors that help him/her learn” with a mean of 3.86 which is interpreted as very evident. These results highlight the learners capacity for introspection and their ability in recognizing effective learning strategies which are then essential in fostering independence and improve academic performance.

On the other hand, item number 4 in before the lesson “Identify barriers to learning” got the lowest rated mean of 3.57 but is still interpreted as very evident. This indicates that learners may find it challenging to pinpoint obstacles prior to instruction and suggests a potential area for enhancement such as incorporating activities or tools that help students reflect on possible hindrances to their learning. This is followed by item number 3 in before the lesson “Identify ideas or concepts s/he misunderstands” with a mean of 3.63 but is still interpreted as very evident. Finally, item number 2 in before the lesson “Understand the purpose of the lesson and how to do well in the lesson” got the third lowest mean of 3.66 but is still interpreted as very evident. This indicates a slight need for greater emphasis on preparatory reflection and suggests that additional scaffolding or explicit discussions about the lesson objectives and potential misconceptions may help learners better engage in the before the lesson phase.

Overall, the data reflect that the formative assessments effectively capture key formative assessment components. The high ratings across all items, even the lowest-scored ones, affirm the formative assessments facilitates self-regulation, introspection, and targeted learning strategies among students. However, opportunities exist to strengthen the before the lesson phase to further support learners in identifying and overcoming barriers and misconceptions before instruction begins.

Table 3. Content of the Instrument (For the Teacher)

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
<i>The formative assessments lets' the teacher...</i>			
A. Before The Lesson			
1. Get information about what the learner already knows and can do about the new lesson	3.80	.45	Very Evident
2. Share learning intentions and success criteria to the learners	3.80	.37	Very Evident
3. Determine misconceptions	3.74	.43	Very Evident
4. Identify what hinders learning	3.69	.38	Very Evident
B. During The Lesson			
1. Provide immediate feedback to learners	3.94	.08	Very Evident
2. Identify what hinders learning	3.91	.08	Very Evident
3. Identify what facilitates learning	3.83	.19	Very Evident
4. Identify learning gaps	3.86	.18	Very Evident
5. Track learner progress in comparison to formative assessment results prior to the lesson proper	3.91	.13	Very Evident
6. To make decision on whether to proceed with the next lesson, re-teach, or provide for corrective measures or reinforcements	3.80	.19	Very Evident
C. After The Lesson			
1. Assess whether learning objectives have been met for a specified duration	3.91	.13	Very Evident

2. Remediate and/ or enrich with appropriate strategies as needed.	3.89	.12	Very Evident
3. Evaluate whether learning intentions and success criteria have been met	3.94	.08	Very Evident
Overall	3.85	.22	Very Evident

Note: 3.50 – 4.00 Very Evident, 2.50 – 3.49 Somehow Evident, 1.50 – 2.49 Rarely Evident, 1.00 – 1.49 Not Evident

Table 3 presents the content of the instrument (for the teacher). This further reveal that most of the items are seen in the formative assessments with an overall mean of 3.848 which is interpreted as very evident. This finding underscore that formative assessments effectively captures critical elements of the teaching process, emphasizing the role of the teacher in fostering student learning and progress.

Moreover, item number 1 in during the lesson “Provide immediate feedback to learners” and item number 3 in after the lesson “Evaluate whether learning intentions and success criteria have been met” got the highest rated mean of 3.94 which is interpreted as very evident. These results emphasize the importance of timely feedback and post-lesson evaluation, which are fundamental to effective formative assessment. Immediate feedback not only aids students in addressing misconceptions but also reinforces correct understanding. Similarly, evaluating whether learning goals have been achieved ensures the alignment of teaching strategies with desired outcomes. This is followed by item number 2 in during the lesson “Identify what hinders learning”, item number 5 in during the lesson “Track learner progress in comparison to formative assessment results prior to the lesson proper”, and item number 1 in after the lesson “Assess whether learning objectives have been met for a specified duration” with a mean of 3.91 which is interpreted as very evident. These items highlight teachers’ ability to diagnose challenges, monitor progress, and assess learning outcomes, all of which contribute to informed instructional decision-making. The third of which is item number 2 in during the lesson “Remediate and/ or enrich with appropriate strategies as needed.” with a mean of 3.89 which is interpreted as very evident. This reflected teachers' proactive efforts in adjusting their instruction based on learners' needs, further emphasizing the dynamic nature of formative assessments.

On the other hand, item number 4 in before the lesson “Identify what hinders learning” got the lowest rated mean of 3.69 but is still interpreted as very evident. This indicates a potential need for greater emphasis on before the lesson diagnostics to identify barriers that could affect student readiness. This is followed by item number 3 in before the lesson “Determine misconceptions” with a mean of 3.74 but is still interpreted as very evident. Finally, item number 1 in before the lesson “Get information about what the learner already knows and can do about the new lesson”, item number 2 in before the lesson “Share learning intentions and success criteria to the learners”, and item number 6 in during the lesson “To make decision on whether to proceed with the next lesson, re-teach, or provide for corrective measures or reinforcements” got the third lowest mean of 3.80 but is still interpreted as very evident.

Overall, these reflects essential practices in lesson preparation and ongoing assessment but highlights areas where additional support or resources might further enhance teachers’ effectiveness. The findings demonstrate that the instrument effectively captures key elements of formative assessment practices from the perspective of the teacher. High-rated items underscore the importance of providing feedback, evaluating progress, and responding dynamically to learners' needs. Meanwhile, the before the lesson phase suggest opportunities for improvement, particularly in enhancing diagnostic measures before instruction begins. By addressing these areas, the instrument can better support teachers in delivering instruction that is both responsive and impactful.

Table 4. *Alignment of the Instrument to the Curriculum*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
A. Before The Lesson			
1. The activities are aligned with the DepEd Curriculum for the particular subject area, grade level, quarter, and topic	3.74	.43	Very Evident
2. The activities are aligned with the Schools’ Curriculum which includes the Vision, Mission, and Thrust	3.77	.44	Very Evident
B. During The Lesson			
1. The activities are aligned with the DepEd Curriculum for the particular subject area, grade level, quarter, and topic	3.91	.13	Very Evident
2. The activities are aligned with the Schools’ Curriculum which includes the Vision, Mission, and Thrust	3.94	.08	Very Evident
C. After The Lesson			
1. The activities are aligned with the DepEd Curriculum for the particular subject area, grade level, quarter, and topic	3.94	.13	Very Evident
2. The activities are aligned with the Schools’ Curriculum which includes the Vision, Mission, and Thrust	3.97	.06	Very Evident
Overall	3.88	.21	Very Evident

Note: 3.50 – 4.00 Very Evident, 2.50 – 3.49 Somehow Evident, 1.50 – 2.49 Rarely Evident, 1.00 – 1.49 Not Evident

Table 4 presents the alignment of the instrument to the curriculum. This further reveal that the formative assessments are aligned with the curriculum with an overall mean of 3.878 which is interpreted as very evident. The findings affirm that the instrument is effectively aligned with the curriculum, ensuring that assessment activities are relevant and purposeful.

Moreover, item number 2 in after the lesson “The activities are aligned with the Schools’ Curriculum which includes the Vision, Mission, and Thrust” got the highest rated mean of 3.97 which is interpreted as very evident. This indicates a strong alignment between

post-lesson activities and the overarching goals and values of the school, emphasizing the importance of integrating institutional objectives into formative assessments. This is followed by item number 2 in during the lesson “The activities are aligned with the Schools’ Curriculum which includes the Vision, Mission, and Thrust” and item number 1 in after the lesson “The activities are aligned with the DepEd Curriculum for the particular subject area, grade level, quarter, and topic” with a mean of 3.94 which is interpreted as very evident. These findings highlight that during and after lesson activities are consistently aligned with both the DepEd (Department of Education) curriculum and the specific goals of the school. This alignment ensures coherence between instructional strategies and desired learning outcomes, fostering meaningful learning experiences for students.

On the other hand, item number 1 in before the lesson “The activities are aligned with the DepEd Curriculum for the particular subject area, grade level, quarter, and topic” got the lowest rated mean of 3.74 but is still interpreted as very evident. While still interpreted as very evident, this rating suggests a slight need for improvement in ensuring that before the lesson activities are more explicitly aligned with the curriculum. This is followed by item number 2 in before the lesson “The activities are aligned with the Schools’ Curriculum which includes the Vision, Mission, and Thrust” with a mean of 3.77 but is still interpreted as very evident. This highlights a potential area of focus for enhancing before the lesson alignment. These slightly lower ratings may point to a gap in the preparatory phase where activities could more rigorously reflect the curriculum’s standards and goals.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that the instrument effectively aligns formative assessments with both the DepEd Curriculum and the schools’ Vision, Mission, and Thrust. This alignment is particularly evident during and after the lesson phases, where activities are strongly connected to curriculum goals. However, there is room for improvement in the before the lesson phase to ensure that all preparatory activities align equally well with the prescribed standards. Addressing these areas can further enhance the instrument’s effectiveness in promoting curriculum-driven formative assessment practices.

Table 5. Pre and Post Test result of the respondents

Proficiency Level	Interpretation	Grace Pass Result		Quarter Exam Result	
		F	%	F	%
Beginning (0 – 19%)	The student at this level struggles with his / her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.	42	18.5	38	16.7
Developing (20 – 39%)	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.	168	74.0	66	29.1
Approaching Proficiency (40 – 59%)	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks	17	7.5	64	28.2
Proficient (60 – 79%)	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.	0	0	41	18.1
Advanced (80 – 100%)	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings, and can transfer them automatically and flexibility through authentic performance tasks	0	0	18	7.9
Total		227	100.0	227	100.0

Table 5 presents the Pre and Post Test result based on the Global Resources for Assessment Curriculum and Evaluation Performance Assessment of Standards and Skills (GRACE PASS) and the Quarter Examination Result of the respondents.

This further reveal that in the GRACE PASS result, 168 or 74.0% are developing, 42 or 18.5% are beginning, 17 or 7.5% are approaching proficiency, and 0 or 0.0% are proficient and advanced. Moreover, in the Quarter Examination result of the respondents, 66 or 29.1% are developing, 64 or 28.2% are approaching proficiency, 41 or 18.1% are proficient, 38 or 16.7% are beginning, and 18 or 7.9% are advanced.

With the following data above, it can be said that the students’ scores increased based on the Global Resources for Assessment Curriculum and Evaluation Performance Assessment of Standards and Skills (GRACE PASS) given as Pre-test and the Quarter Examination Result for the Post-test. From 42 in the beginning it decreased to 38, from 168 in the developing it decreased to 66 left, from 17 in the approaching proficiency it increased to 64, from 0 in the proficient it increased to 41, and from 0 in the advanced it increased to 18.

Conclusions

Formative assessments play a critical role in achieving mathematics learning goals by fostering self-regulation, introspection, and targeted strategies among students, while empowering teachers to provide timely feedback and make informed instructional decisions. The results indicate that these assessments are effectively aligned with the curriculum, ensuring relevance and coherence with educational standards and institutional objectives. While the formative assessments are highly effective during and after the lesson

phases, opportunities for enhancement exist in the before the lesson phase. Addressing these gaps by incorporating diagnostic tools and explicitly aligning preparatory activities with curriculum goals can further strengthen their impact. Overall, the findings demonstrate that formative assessments contribute significantly to improved student performance and engagement in mathematics. With these, it is recommended that the formative assessments before the lesson should be refined and be provided with additional support to both learners and educators to better achieve meaningful learning experiences and academic success.

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